

The Dark Universe

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Anomalous velocities, gravitational lensing, Big Bang theory, and consistency with understood physics strongly suggest that over 80% of all mass in the Universe is invisible, cold, non-baryonic matter. While myriad speculation surrounds dark matter, modern empirical observations and simulations of its distribution and mass are being articulated with accuracy. Dark matter must play a commanding role in the evolution of galaxies, galaxy clusters, and the Universe at large.

Bizarre Velocity Measurements

Visionary scientist Fritz Zwicky first provided methods and evidence for the presence of unseen matter in 1933. He clearly explained how within the Coma galaxy cluster, the “internal viscosity due to the gravitational interactions of its component masses is so high as to cause it to rotate like a solid body” (1). He led the use of the virial theorem to articulate the “missing mass problem”, relating the average kinetic energy of galaxies with the total gravitational binding energy:

$$2\langle T \rangle = n\langle V_{TOT} \rangle$$

For decades after Zwicky's initial observations, virtually no more significant work supported that the mass to light ratio was anything other than unity. Then in 1970, Vera Rubin changed that. She presented controversial findings based on a new sensitive spectrograph that could measure the velocity curve of edge-on spiral galaxies to a greater degree of accuracy than had ever before been achieved (2). With Kent Ford, Rubin would later publish the stunning discovery that most

stars surveyed in 21 spiral galaxies orbit at roughly the same speed, contrary to expectations (3).

Figure 1 | Anomalous rotation curve of a typical spiral galaxy. The dashed line (A) shows the motion for stars that Newtonian mechanics would predict, while the solid line (B) shows the observed uniform motion. The rotation of seemingly-disconnected stars is awfully similar to that of a rigid “solid body” (*e.g.* a planet), as originally suggested by Zwicky (1934).

Either Newtonian mechanics diverge into alternative paradigms on galactic scales (as they diverge on quantum scales), or most of all galactic mass is invisible. Both scenarios would clearly have staggering implications, and so should each should be explored very carefully.

Failure of Newtonian Mechanics, or Failure to See Most of Everything?

Classical mechanics describes how the force between two particles is some exponential function of the distance between them. But this may not always be true, considering, *e.g.*, tidal dwarf galaxies, which have stars that can settle into unusual states of dynamical relaxation due to broader physical environments (4).

Within the historical context of revolutions in scientific paradigms (*e.g.* Einstein's relativity), it should not be so radical to consider with great depth that we don't really understand the physics being observed. Indeed, significant work has been done on (5) and around (6) the theoretical study of

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Modified Newtonian Dynamics (“MOND”), which seeks to explain the anomalous observations in stellar mechanics without invoking a colossal amount of invisible matter. As one of many alternative paradigms, MOND is characterized by the premise that the gravitational force between two particles is based upon the *accelerations* of particles, rather than their *distance* (reconsidering the role of $F=ma$ in gravitation).

But such comprehensive revisions of mechanics are popularly controversial, to say the least. The fact is that most astronomers and astrophysicists today have reasonably and conservatively coalesced around the explanation that over 80% of all matter is invisible. One of the strongest arguments against new mechanical regimes like MOND is the dynamically-independent technique for measuring mass: *gravitational lensing*.

Gravitational Lensing Reveals Mass of the Universe Independently

Gravitational lensing is perhaps the smoking gun for the existence of dark matter. A gravitational lens is formed when the light from a distant source (such as a quasar) is “bent” around a massive object (such as a cluster of galaxies) between the source object and the observer (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 | Illustration of gravitational lensing. Light is bent around a massive object from a bright source directly behind it. The orange arrows show the

perceived positions of the background source, while the white arrows show the actual path of the light from the true position of the source. *Image Credit: NASA*

By measuring the distortion geometry, the mass of the cluster causing the phenomena can be obtained. We can calculate the mass of the lens using general relativistic equations, and thus can use gravitational lensing to independently measure the mass of large distributions in our Universe.

By measuring the shapes and distortions of half a million galaxies with the Hubble Space Telescope, and then reconstructing the distribution of intervening mass along line of sight, Massey et al. (2007) were able to make high-fidelity maps of the large-scale distribution of dark matter, which are resolved in both angle and depth (7). In other words, they mapped dark matter three-dimensionally (Figure 3).

Figure 3 | Three-dimensional reconstruction of dark matter distribution. Using gravitational lensing data from the Hubble Space Telescope, Massey et al. (2007) published this vivid depiction of the clumpy nature of dark matter in *Nature* (7). The three axes correspond to right ascension, declination and redshift: with distance from the Earth increasing towards the bottom.

They found “a loose network of filaments, growing over time, which intersect in massive structures at the locations of clusters of galaxies”. Their findings

are consistent with the broader avant-garde observational literature implicating dark matter, placing invaluable constraints on models seeking to explain these problems. Indeed, the stunning insight acquired by gravitational lensing informs the scientific community that dark matter likely plays a leading role in the ageing of the Universe.

Non-Baryonic Matter as a Necessary Compactor of the Universe

The Concordance Model, which is an evolving cosmological canon seeking to explain the Universe, holds that baryonic matter (*i.e.* fused protons and neutrons) was too hot, upon forming after the Big Bang, to coalesce by gravity into very compact structures (8). Indeed, according to such theory, if all matter in the Universe was baryonic, then stars, *e.g.*, could not have formed via the Jeans instability:

$$\frac{dp}{dr} = -\frac{G\rho M_{enc}}{r^2}$$

Deep technical insight into Big Bang nucleosynthesis can be used to accurately determine the baryon fraction of the matter density in the Universe. In concert with analyses of galaxy cluster dynamics and the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) radiation, this insight yields well-supported arguments for the existence of a large amount of *non-baryonic* matter (*i.e.* unusual atomic structure). The total matter content of the Universe seems to be at least a factor of five higher than the *maximum* amount of baryonic matter implied by Big Bang nucleosynthesis (9).

Perhaps the strongest argument in favor of non-baryonic dark matter comes from large-scale structure formation and the CMB. The high degree of uniformity and scale-invariance of the most distant and extensive radiation observed in the Universe supports inflationary theory: expansion caused by the Big Bang. Major inconsistencies arise in any inflationary theory that should lead to the observed large-scale structure of the Universe *if* non-baryonic matter does *not* play a leading role in compacting the Universe.

With baryons only, the recombination of electrons with hydrogen and helium nuclei would have occurred too late relative to the time when the CMB radiation was first emitted, and so the highly nonlinear structures observed today do not seem possible without a matter-dominated Universe *before* the baryonic recombination. The theoretical feasibility of this paradigm is supported by large numerical simulations of structure formation (9).

Computer Simulations on Evolution of Galaxies and Dark Matter

Simulating the formation, evolution, and clustering of galaxies is a very elusive process that demands strong observational *and* theoretical inputs. Two problems have so far prevented any great accuracy. First, there is an extreme range of interactivity to be represented among populations of large, multifaceted, non-linear systems like galaxy *clusters*, which must maintain a depth of resolution that is high enough to engender the formation of individual *galaxies*, which necessarily describe the orbits of billions of *stars*... Second, beyond this impossible computational problem, a host of non-trivial factors behind galaxy-formation physics are uncertain. These must be treated by trial and error. And despite the degree of aesthetic and parameterized consistency, simulated products must necessarily be intellectually treated with the same degree of skepticism as the questionable parameters that define them.

Nonetheless, modern computer simulations are a very powerful means of testing our understanding. Possibly the most advanced simulation ever, a supercomputing *N*-body known as the *Millennium Simulation*, calculated the evolution of dark matter structure using $2,160^3$ particles, ultimately supporting the perception that dark matter and galaxies are a *continuous cosmic web* (10). The tight network of cold dark matter and galactic clusters can be observed in Figure 4. On larger scales, there is little discernible structure, while resolved dark matter substructures are visible orbiting cluster haloes once zoomed in.

Figure 4 | Dark matter density on various scales. Springel et al. (2005) use each individual image to show the projected dark matter density field, color-coded by density and local dark matter velocity dispersion. The zoom sequence displays consecutive enlargements by factors of four, centered on one of the many galaxy cluster haloes present in their simulation.

Dark Matter Probably Moves Slowly

In addition to requiring about 4/5 of all matter to be non-baryonic matter, the Concordance Model currently holds that dark matter is *cold*: it moves much slower than the speed of light. Cold dark matter seems necessary in order for it to compress into the clumpy structures implied, and thus catalyze the baryonic matter into the non-linear structures observed (8). The dynamical nature is

an important distinction to make, compared to dark matter being 'hot' (speeds that are ultra-relativistic, or approximately the speed of light) or even 'warm' (speeds that are relativistic, or approaching the speed of light). Under those regimes, by any standards, we would expect a radically-chaotic visual of the Universe!

This is why the Concordance Model is now called the *Lambda CDM* model, where 'CDM' stands for

Cold Dark Matter, and ‘ Λ ’ points to the use of a major cosmological constant for equalizing known physics: “*dark energy*”.

Discussion and Conclusion

There is no shortage of hypotheses seeking to explain dark matter. Imaginative astrophysicists have invented dozens of paradigms, some very robust and others not so much, which seek to integrate observed inconsistencies. There is a chance that we are just wrong dynamically, but there is also strong, independent lines of evidence suggesting a lot of invisible matter.

It is important to note that no paradigm, even the well-supported cold non-baryonic matter regime, is without significant flaws. This is through no fault of our own: the Concordance Model is simply the most consistent explanations that we have under extreme information limitations. Every possible explanation of dark matter requires ‘extensions’ of known physics. Such creativity is necessary. But I am skeptical of what we believe, and of what we can hardly prove to be false.

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So what is dark matter? Well, if we want any answer that makes any sense, we need more information on the *dynamics* of dark matter. Otherwise, we can liken this question to asking: “What is atomic matter?”, but literally with *zero* knowledge of the physics, chemistry, and every other scale of interactivity of such matter.

But I am not so cynical about the long-term future. Considering our impressive history of innovation, and the naturally accelerating advances in science, I predict an exciting drama of discovery and scientific revolution unfolding in a matter of only a few decades; science should continue hacking away at this immense frontier until then. Answering “What is dark matter?” with any confidence will require enormous developments in relevant hard data, from many disciplines. And a full answer may never really emerge. But we can expect sharp advances in our understanding of dark matter from such flagship science endeavors as the Large Hadron Collider, the James Webb Space Telescope, GAIA, and LISA; as well as the sustained work on this issue from many thousands of leading researchers worldwide.